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GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: A REVIEW AND RESEARCH DIRECTION

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ABSTRACT

Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) has appeared as an environmental innovation which integrates environmental concerns into supply chain management. GSCM has gained popularity with both academic and practitioners. The purpose of the paper is to briefly review the recent literatures of the GSCM and also determine the new direction area of this emerging field. A detailed review is used to sort out the literature and develop the research direction of the study. The review is focused on development of GSCM in a developed and developing countries including all those researchers which is relevant to environmental and social sustainability towards operation management and the supply chain. It shows that lack researches to examine the adoption and implementation of GSCM practices especially in developing countries such as Malaysia. Thus, the authors bring forward a proposed research direction on GSCM adoption and implementation in Malaysia's manufacturing industries.

KEYWORDS

Supply Chain Management, Green Supply Chain Management, Environmental Management, ISO 14001 Certified Manufacturing Firms

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ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN THE SUPPLY CHAIN OF FRUITS & VEGETABLES SECTOR IN INDIA: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Purpose- The entire supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables in India is laden with various issues and challenges. To list the possible challenges and suggest a way forward, there is a need to study the supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables sector in India. So the purpose of this paper is to discuss the supply chain of fruits and vegetables sector in India and explain the issues which are affecting it. Authors also suggested the corresponding mitigation strategies to overcome the identified issues and challenges.

Design/methodology/approach- Descriptive research has been used for this study. The supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables sector has been explained and attempt has been made towards identifying the issues affecting the supply chain of the sector. The present study undertakes a thorough review of basic and contemporary literature available and tries to explain the factors affecting the supply chain of Fruits and Vegetables sector in India.

The literature has been divided into various themes according to the issues in the supply chain and an investigation has been attempted to identify various factors affecting the supply chain.

Findings- The study found that Cold Chain Facilities; Fragmented Supply Chain; Linkages and Integration between the partners; Taxation Issue; Infrastructure Facilities; Cost of Packaging Material; Technology and Techniques; Farmer's Knowledge and Awareness; Quality and Safety standards; Processing and Value Addition; Supply Chain inefficiency; Farmers income; Supply chain losses and wastage of fresh produce; Transportation facilities; Demand and market information etc. are the factors which constitutes serious challenges for Fruits and Vegetables sector and are affecting the overall growth of the agricultural development of India.

Research limitations/implications- The authors have focuses only on Fruits and Vegetables sector, authors may look at other sector like food processing unit, cold chain and other perishable items such as meat, dairy industry, chocolate, beverages etc.

Practical implications- Overcoming these issues and challenges will benefit the decision makers and various stakeholders like the farmers, state government, transporters and food

processing unit to understand the current status, issues and challenges for better planning and management in the field of fruits and vegetables supply chain.

Originality/value- Most of the prior literature have been focused on the general issues like cold chain, marketing efficiency etc. of fruit and vegetables supply chain. There exists a need of having review on supply chain specifically in F&V sector, identifying all the factors affecting it and suggest mitigation strategies. This review fills this gap in the literature of supply chain management of Fruits and Vegetables sector.

Keywords:

Fruits & Vegetables, Supply Chain Management, Inefficiency, Infrastructure, Wastage.

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Application of Fishbone Analysis for Evaluating Supply Chain and Business Process A CASE STUDY ON THE ST JAMES HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Conducting business is certainly not the easiest things to do in this hyper-competitive business fraternity. The scenario for the manufacturing firms is even more challenging as their value chain are the longest and widest by every considerations. Therefore, it is immensely vital for the manufacturing operators to analyze their supply chain properly so that they can establish a real good one in their armoury. The fishbone analyse is a tool for analyzing the business process and its effectiveness. It is also commonly referred as “Ishikawa Diagram” because it was invented and incorporated by Mr. Kaoru Ishikawa, a Japanese quality control statistician. It is defined as a fishbone because of its structural outlook and appearance. The fishbone analyse is a tool for analyzing the business process and its effectiveness. This study was intended towards evaluating the supply chain and business process of St. James Hospital. The analysis reveals that the problem areas are lack of proper equipment, faulty process, misdirected people, poorly materials managed, improper environment, and inefficient management.

KEYWORDS

Fishbone, St James Hospital, Business Process, Supply Chain

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EMERGING SUPPLIER SELECTION CRITERIA IN THE CONTEXT OF TRADITIONAL VS GREEN SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Supply chain management used to be widely understood as an integrated one-way manufacturing process, in which the raw material is converted to the finished product and then delivered to the customer. It merely centered around the procurement of raw material to make the final product. With increasing concern towards environmental protection, organizations have become more and more responsible for their products and overall sustainability. For companies to maintain their sustainability and competitiveness in the market, green supply chain management (GSCM) considers a systematic and integrated approach. It has been found from the literature that the green supplier selection is an important issue in improving environmental related performance. This study attempts to find out what the traditional supply chain is and how to redefine the basic structure of traditional supply chain. It also explores major factors included in green supply chain along with the criteria for supplier selection process.

KEYWORDS

Supplier selection, Supplier selection methods, Supplier selection criterion, Green supply chain management (GSCM).

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SUPPLY CHAIN INTEGRATION - A COMPETENCY BASED PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to signify the effect of inherent critical competencies on supply chain integration. A theoretical framework is proposed linking managerial, organizational and interorganizational competencies with supply chain integration and performance. Propositions are posited with suggestions for further research. Simultaneously, present paper looks at strategizing the different practices involved in successful management of a supply chain emphasizing on intra (internal consistency) and inter-organizational (external consistency) relations. The paper provides value to the academicians and practitioners in both the fields by focussing on the impact competencies have on supply chain management system. The results are expected to provide an integrated (intra and inter-organizational) perspective to academicians looking at studying competencies in the field of supply chain.

KEYWORDS

Competencies, inter-organizational competencies, supply chain integration, supply chain performance

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DYNAMICS OF GARMENT SUPPLY CHAIN

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to examine the supply chain structure of the garment industry in India. Indian garment industry is one of the leading garment industries in the world, which is full of diversities and complexities. The study aims at examining the existing structure of the supply chain at every level from raw material to the garment production until it reaches to the customer. The study also focuses on investigating the major supply chain challenges and aims at suggesting the proper supply chain framework. This is an exploratory research study which examines the structures and various issues concerned at every level of the supply chain. The study is based on the data available from the secondary sources as well as the review of literature from the available sources. The study finds that the Indian garment industry is facing many supply chain issues such as inventory management, visibility, lead time, collaboration, technology and logistics which are almost faced by all the companies all over the supply chain. The companies also vary in their size and are product offerings base on their target customer groups. Study also suggests the appropriate supply chain strategy for every combination of company type and product offered.

KEYWORDS

Garment Industry, Supply chain management, Quick response, Inventory management, Collaboration, product specific supply chain, India

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A New Fuzzy DEMATEL-TODIM Hybrid Method for evaluation criteria of Knowledge management in supply chain

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ABSTRACT

Knowledge management (KM) adoption in the supply chain network needs a good investment as well as few changes in the culture of the entire SC. Knowledge management is the process of creating, distributing and transferring information. The goal of this study is to Rank KM criteria in supply chain network in Iran which is important for firms these days. Criterion used in this paper were extracted from the literature review and were confirmed by supply chain experts. The proposed approach for ranking and finding out about these criterion is hybrid fuzzy DEMATEL-TODIM, with using fuzzy number as data for our studies we could avoid uncertainty. The data was gathered from PhD. And Ms. Students in industrial engineering of Kharrazmi university of Tehran and PhD. And Ms. Students of the management department of Semnan university. A new hybrid approach was used for achieving the results of this study. This new hybrid approach ranks data criteria respect to each other, then by using TODIM for ranking respect to the best situation (gains), the rates of criterion were determined which is a very important advantage.

KEYWORDS

Knowledge management (KM), Supply chain, Fuzzy DEMATEL, Fuzzy TODIM

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Intensification of the supply chain by the storing of trajectories data

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ABSTRACT

To improve the profitability and the quality of services, and to confront the difficult competition, companies are in search of the effective approaches to improve their professions in general, and the management of the supply chain in particular which plays an essential role for reduction of cost, the improvement of the quality of services, and increase of the productivity. This work aims to improve the performance of supply chain by the conception of trajectories data warehouse intended to collect the data relative to the mobile objects. The information stored in the data warehouse will be analyzed to extract knowledge which we use to a decision-making and leading to strengthen the management of the supply chain.

KEYWORDS

Supply chain, Mobile objects, Trajectory data warehouse

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Managing Green Supply Chain: Initiatives and Outcomes

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ABSTRACT

Reacting to increasingly stringent government regulations and rising consumer demands for more sustainable products, and also to create competitive advantages, many companies have begun implementing sustainability practices in their strategy and everyday are done in the area of environment friendly supply chain practices adopted by large corporate houses across the globe. Due to their enormous economic and environmental impact on society with their extensive networks of suppliers and customers supply chain practices, will help us the gap between theory and practice chain management practices adopted by strategies adopted by Hewlett Packard, Coca Cola, Dutch flower industry and Bank of America and how they have made huge profits as has been included in this paper. The research also throws light on the initiatives taken in this field by Indian companies and how a major progress can be driven in this perspective

KEYWORDS

Green Supply chain management, Sustainability, Going Green, Product Development

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MONTE CARLO SIMULATION BASED PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SUPPLY CHAINS

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ABSTRACT

Since supply chain management is one of the most important management practices that impacts the financial results of services and companies, it is important to optimize and analyze the performance of supply chains. Simulation provides a way to get closer to real life complex situations and uses less simplifications and assumptions than needed with analytical solutions. This paper proposes the application of Monte Carlo simulation based optimization and sensitivity analysis of supply chains to handle modeling uncertainties and stochastic nature of the processes and to extract and visualize relationship among the decision variables and the Key Performance Indicators. In this article the authors utilize their own interactive simulator, SIMWARE, capable to simulate complex multi-echelon supply chains based on simple configurable connection of building blocks. They introduce a sensitivity analysis technique to extract and visualize the relationships among the decision variables and key performance indicators. . The proposed robust sensitivity analysis is based on an improved method used to extract gradients from Monte Carlo simulation. The extracted gradients (sensitivities) are visualized by a technique developed by the authors. The results illustrate that the sensitivity analysis tool is flexible enough to handle complex situations and straightforward and simple enough to be used for decision support.

KEYWORDS

Multi-echelon supply chain, service level, safety stock, Monte Carlo simulation, sensitivity analysis, optimization, visualization

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